

PREVENTION OF CONFLICTS BETWEEN STUDENTS AS A NECESSARY PROBLEM

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Abstract. *This article presents the conflicts that arise between students, their types, causes, ways to solve them. In addition, there are ideas about ways to prevent conflicts based on the pedagogical and psychological characteristics of pedagogical conflicts.*

Keywords: *conflict, conflict, administrative conflict, pedagogical conflict, optimization, globalization, motivational conflict, moral conflict.*

Modern people today have their own content and socialization living in a complex world according to its trends. In the process of human survival, society continues to develop, between which there is always a variety of discord, contentious reflections and arguments that lead to conflict situations.

In addition to developments, updates, changes and technological processes in the psychological pedagogical sphere, there is an increasing use of new technologies, internet resources in the educational system. The term "conflict" comes from the Latin word conflict - conflict. The very concept of "conflict" is distinguished by a very wide range of content and is used in various meanings. In the most general sense, conflict can be described as "the final escalation of contradictions". Sufficiently based on the definition of the concept of "conflict". There is a classification proposed by Shepansky, that is, he interprets the dispute as "a conflict of purpose and opportunity that arises due to a specific subject or situation, calling for opposite orientation."

Historically, it is known that in ancient times, the elders of the clan - the Council of tribal chiefs served as the decisive force for the dispute. But in the later stages of human history, it is natural that the emergence of the first states, the stratification between people, the evolution of different political systems, and the emergence of various political systems behind it, does not always ensure stability in society.

Such changes have exacerbated a certain level of social injustice among people. As a result, the ground was broken for disputes, and the contradictions between the parties continued to expand. As a result, the problems of his influence were growing behind the conflict with the society. Therefore, over the past many years, the Society of man has been looking forward to a peaceful future, always striving to see a society without war and confrontation.

Among the first views and concepts about the nature of social conflicts, ancient Greek philosophers have a special place. The famous ancient philosopher Heraclitus tried to link his thoughts and mulochases in the turmoil of wars and social conflicts to a system of general views on natural existence. Until then, the raw thing is interconnected and grows together. Including the norms of human attitude.

The qomusi scholar Abu Nasr Farabi (873-950 ce) was the first to examine the system of scientific-theoretical knowledge of the origins of jamiyam and how to govern the state.

Forobi believes that one reason for conflicts in society is that social life, city - state, morality and thought in the thinking of people are not fully formed. Speaking about the Prevention

of conflicts that are going to arise in turn, as well as the fact that the knowledge that people receive in these sciences, yuwori, gives positive results, justifies the fact that the acquisition of theoretical knowledge is important in practice. Forobius' reflections on society show the "doctrine of violence and coercion". Because in any state and society, the reflection of the "doctrine of violence and coercion" in practice is the basis of the formation of conflicts in that state and society. Contrary to the Faroese "doctrine of violence and coercion", O'laroch advances "theory of natural need"^{N1}. The fact that Zero people live together in harmony, organize into communities, spend days helping each other are natural signs of the existence of a "natural need" in nature and society.

Based on the analysis of a large number of domestic and foreign works N.V. Grishina proposes to define socio-psychological conflict as "a conflict that arises and persists in the field of communication, arising in the context of conflicting goals, behaviors, attitudes of people, their desire to achieve any goals."

In the context of interaction, an individual's behavioral strategy is determined by the fact that he wants to satisfy his own interests (passive or active action) and the interests of the other party (acting together or individually). Thus, in conditions of interaction, people behave differently, therefore, natural questions arise about the reasons for a person's choice of one or another behavioral strategy, about personal characteristics that affect behavior in a particular situation.

Conflict as a socio-psychological phenomenon, its essence, structure and typology A.Ya. studied in the works of. Antsupova, A.I. Shipilova, N.V. Grishina, V.P. Ratnikova, N.I. Leonova, E.A. Rodionova et al. the problem of choosing a behavioral strategy in conflict is that many authors (Scott J. G., Thomas K., Kenneth R., Grishina N.V. and others) in their works and their appearance, the issue of personal factors is considered. Gromova O N., Krichevsky R.L., Antsupov A.Ya., Shipilov A.I. and others dealt with disputes separately.

In the literature, participants in the conflict can be individual individs, social groups and organizations.

The main participants in the dispute are the opposite Saiy-acting partners. They form a conflict core. The conflict stops when at least one of the main parties comes out of the struggle of contradictions. It is usually said that conflict refers to oppositely oriented views, to conflicts expressed through intergroup or interpersonal relationships associated with unpleasant emotional experiences .

When interpreted from a psychological point of view, the aspect that has a devastating effect on people is not the conflicts themselves, but their consequence. In the course of disputes, negative feelings arise in the human psyche, such as fear, panic, enmity. If these experiences are strong and last for a long time, a protective reaction can occur and strengthen in a person.

Negative states in the outcome of a dispute make certain changes in the personality's emotion, behavior, thinking and character of the letter. These changes are manifested in the behavior of the individual, and the subject in question also spreads to other situations in which he is participating and begins to occupy a wide range of areas of interaction. For example, it is unlikely that a person raised in an environment of fear and danger will later become the source of a similar environment. He even raises his children in such an environment or leads the family in this style.

Any dispute has its own reasons and comes to the face on the basis of the need to satisfy some need. Due to the value capable of satisfying this need and its possession, the origin of the

dispute is considered its object. In the formation of the personality of the reader, the environment in which he lives, the role of society is very large. Another factor in the reasons for the origin of conflicts is the fact that living conditions are not good. In the case of a bad lifestyle in students not only the teacher, but also a state of conflict with the side surrounding subjects and a state of a severe psychological process can occur. Conflicts from a psychological point of view, as opposed to pedagogical and psychological sciences are inextricably linked. Both of them research the general process of life – the psychic activity of a person, as well as his behavior. Since preventing conflicts between students in this regard is a difficult problem, it is unlikely that a modern teacher will not be a social psychologist. Therefore, it is necessary to be able to establish their relationship between students, to know the use of pedagogical-psychological mechanisms in the children's community. As noted above, contentious behavior consists of the actions of the parties, expressed outwardly. The quality of a particular form of interaction consists in the fact that their uniqueness is aimed at preventing the opponent from pursuing his goals and pursuing his own personal goals. Conflict and conflict exist from the time of the emergence of mankind, the first views on the study of it as a subject of scientific research have its own history.

As long as students interact with one another, conflicts of different appearance arise between them. To prevent this from happening, the teacher must anticipate measures to prevent conflicts between students. Frequent recurrences of such conflicts among the student youth can also be observed in cases of fading of the attitude of educators towards their profession and professional deformation in the teacher. Therefore, in pedagogical psychological research, the prevention of conflicts in pedagogical activity, their elimination remains an urgent problem.

With the concept of the social environment, the ground on which the conflict arises and develops is determined.

Adolescence is a difficult period for both the parent and the child.

Conflicts between parents and adolescents are often reflected in all subsequent relationships. Adolescents are subject to conflict under the influence of the society around them, friends, transitional age, etc. Each person goes through this stage of his development. But in our time, free access to the Internet and social networks, these reasons are becoming more and more [5]. Of course, the family is very important and necessary for every person. It is unique in its own way, since there is no place to meet outside the family, since several people communicate with each other for a long time and do not leave the family and break off relations with each other. Of course, family members have conflict-prone situations. It should be noted that the position of a teenager in the family is largely determined by the background that governs him. If a teenager feels the affection of his parents, they treat him with caution, but do not bother, then this difficult period of growth will go smoothly for the child. Many conflicts arise from misunderstandings. Adults and children look at the same problem differently. Children want to be independent and free, while parents want to protect their children from the mistakes they once made, limit the choice of children's behavior and prevent the self-realization of children who are the cause of conflicts. As a result, communication and respect are lost. There is a break in the relationship. One of the main reasons for the gap is the influence of the internet and social networks on a teenager. Social media affects both the teenager and the parents. The transition period is a psychologically difficult period for a teenager, since during this period he moves from childhood to adulthood, so adolescents often quarrel with their parents. During this period, it is difficult for parents to control their child, and for him, in turn, it is difficult to understand his parents.

The ever-improving way of life, cocktail activities, the changing attitude of individuals indicate the existence of specific aspects of conflict. In social life, in interpersonal relationships, some special conflicts, mutual disagreements are inevitable. When interpreted from a psychological point of view, the aspect that has a devastating effect on people is not the conflicts themselves, but their consequence.

Teachers prevent conflicts that arise between students different students can acquire and learn independently through different sources. For their parents or independent learning, they will have the opportunity to gain knowledge if they are outnumbered by teachers (repeaters). While science is not well known by the tutors, it studies a part of Science and exposes the knowledge that the teacher is giving on this topic. The practical action of an educator as a specialist on the path to the prevention, elimination of negative pedagogical conflicts, in search of measures, expresses his work on himself.

As a leader of students, the teacher must ensure the full performance of his creative tasks in educational institutions and form pedagogical orientation. It is necessary that the teacher has the opportunity to provide pedagogical, psychological, pedagogical assistance to the participants in the pedagogical dispute. Types of pedagogical and psychological assistance provided to the subjects of pedagogical conflict:

- counseling;
- providing information support;
- diagnosis;
- organizing practical trainings;

In conclusion, it is worth saying that by studying and analyzing the pedagogical-psychological characteristics of conflicts that arise in the pedagogical activity of the teacher, finding their comprehensive ways and applying them in practice

eliminate conflicts prevent the emergence of professional deformities

helps to get. Studying the change in the character of interaction between students makes it possible to distinguish certain states that participate as determinants of the behavior's later patterns.

Thus, the most important condition for the implementation of the personality-developing potential of conflict interactions is the position of subjectivity of the psychologist.

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